

Assessing Amount, Composition, and Physical Properties of Waste for Energy Recovery: Evidence from Panvel Municipal Corporation

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Abstract:

Present study analyses the amount, composition, and physical properties of municipal solid waste (MSW) in Panvel Municipal Corporation (PMC) to assess its waste-to-energy (WTE) potential. Using data from July 2020 to May 2024, the research highlights waste generation patterns across categories such as mixed, wet, dry, domestic hazardous, and sanitary waste. Findings reveal that wet waste, largely organic in nature, dominates the waste stream, followed by mixed and dry waste, underscoring opportunities for composting, biogas, and energy recovery. Seasonal fluctuations and socio-economic factors significantly influence waste volumes, while hazardous and sanitary waste exhibit volatility, demanding specialized handling. The study also emphasizes the role of recycling, informal waste pickers, and revenue generation from recyclables. By linking waste characterization to sustainable management strategies, the research contributes to designing efficient, socially acceptable, and environmentally viable WTE solutions for rapidly urbanizing regions like Panvel.

Keywords: Physical Characterization, Waste to Energy, Recovery, Composition, Panvel Municipal Corporation

Introduction

Solid waste encompasses all rubbish, solid, and semi-solid waste materials inside a community, with the exception of night soil. Both organic and inorganic materials can be found in solid waste. The complete process of handling solid waste, from gathering it from its original source to properly disposing of it to prevent it from becoming an annoyance or endangering the nearby community, is referred to as solid waste management. Management of waste generation, storage at the source of generation, primary collection, street cleaning, temporary storage at the locality level, and regular and intermittent transportation of this temporarily collected waste to disposal sites and treatment plants are all included in solid waste management (Kumar and R.K. 2013).

Creating a draft solid waste management (SWM) strategy for an urban local authority is emphasized in the 2016 SWM regulations. The National Urban Sanitation Policy (NUSP), the National Green Tribunal (NGT), the city's master plan, and sanitation plans should all be taken into consideration while developing the SWM plan's objectives. In-depth analyses of population density, waste production, land availability, institutional structures, technology, economics, and community involvement are required when designing an integrated SWM system. The CPHEEO Manual on Solid Waste Management requires a ULB to create a 20–25

year solid waste management (SWM) plan. The following sections offer some methods to aid in the creation of the ISWM plan at the local level (Cheela et al. 2021).

The design and implementation of an effective solid waste management system are crucial for ensuring proper sanitation and a clean environment. This study focuses on the findings and analysis of waste characterization in the Panvel Municipal Corporation (PMC) area.

It explores the amount of waste generated, its composition, and its physical properties based on samples collected from different locations within Panvel town. The study also addresses the economic aspects related to solid waste management, including the income generated from waste and the utilization of waste products. This includes examining how the waste generated by the community is repurposed and utilized after its initial use. These insights are essential for developing strategies to manage solid waste efficiently and sustainably in urban areas like Panvel.

Today's society is far more conscious of its actions and the effects they have on the environment, and it is more worried about the environment overall. Sustainable waste management is required by society. The use of suitable technology that is socially, economically, and environmentally acceptable is necessary for the effective management of solid waste (Salha Mohammed Kassim 2012).

The formulation of a waste treatment strategy heavily relies on knowledge of the characteristics and volumes of trash. Geographical location, socioeconomic status, eating practices, weather patterns, and industrial activity all affect the makeup of MSW (Cheela et al. 2021). In the present study, the stable generation patterns of mixed waste over time suggest a consistent production of undifferentiated waste in the PMC area. This consistency points to a need for improved waste segregation practices at the source, emphasizing public education and infrastructure development to enhance waste separation efficiency (Aniket R Ingole, Rizvee, and Changhode 2020).

The significant volume of wet waste, predominantly composed of organic materials such as food waste and yard trimmings, indicates the importance of developing efficient organic waste management strategies. This could include composting programs and biogas generation to reduce landfill burden and create valuable by-products. MSW with the major components of organic waste, such as rubbish, green waste, vegetable waste, market waste, kitchen waste, canteen waste, farm waste, etc. are important feed stocks for biogas production. The quantity of MSW is growing quickly as a result of population growth and urbanization. According to reports, domestic households account for 85% of all MSW, of which 51% is organic garbage. garbage management is becoming an increasingly difficult task for growing nations like India. The greatest option for minimizing these issues is to convert garbage into electricity (Aniket R Ingole, Rizvee, and Changhode 2020).

The data for wet waste shows an initial stable period, followed by fluctuations and significant drops, particularly in February 2022. This pattern suggests that external factors, such as changes in population behavior or seasonal impacts, significantly affect the generation of

organic waste. The gradual recovery observed from April 2023 onwards highlights the potential effectiveness of waste management interventions or changes in waste generation habits over time. This finding is in tune with the previous research which showed a statistically and quantitatively significant correlation between the culture of local waste management and individual recycling behavior. It also found that people from regions with higher recycling prevalence are more likely to recycle in their own region (Yiannis Kountouris 2022). The results contribute to the body of research on the connection between culture and behavior, indicating that variations in norms within a nation can have a big impact on an individual's behavior (Alesina A and P 2015; Atkin D 2016; L, P, and L 2009; P and M 2011) .

Methodology for Characterization of MSW in the PMC area

The characterization of municipal solid waste (MSW) in the PMC area involves several key processes. Firstly, it includes the physical sorting and segregation of solid waste into different categories based on its physical properties. This helps in understanding the types and quantities of waste produced in the area. Secondly, the characterization involves analyzing both the physical and chemical characteristics of the solid waste. This analysis provides insights into the makeup of the waste, such as its moisture content, density, calorific value, and presence of hazardous substances. Furthermore, the characterization assesses the overall amount of solid waste generated and its composition in terms of different materials like organic matter, plastics, paper, metals, and others. This detailed examination helps in formulating effective waste management strategies tailored to the specific characteristics of the waste in the PMC area.

Results and Findings

Physical Characteristics of MSW

The table presents data on the distribution of solid waste types in the PMC area from July 2020 to May 2024. The types of solid waste are categorized into Mixed, Wet, Dry, Domestic Hazardous, and Sanitary. Each entry in the table represents the quantity of waste (in tonnes) for each type and month. From July 2020 to May 2024, the data shows variations in the quantities of different types of solid waste.

For instance, the Mixed waste category remains relatively stable over time, indicating consistent generation patterns. Wet waste, which includes organic materials, generally shows higher quantities compared to other types, reflecting typical waste composition in urban areas where food waste and similar materials contribute significantly. Dry waste, which includes materials like paper, plastics, and metals, also demonstrates consistent levels across the months. Domestic Hazardous waste and Sanitary waste, characterized by items requiring special handling due to health or environmental risks, show relatively lower and more stable quantities compared to Mixed and Wet waste categories.

The data highlights seasonal and possibly operational variations in waste generation, which could be influenced by factors such as population dynamics, economic activities, and public awareness campaigns on waste management practices. Such insights are crucial for municipal

authorities in devising effective waste management strategies tailored to the specific characteristics and trends observed in the PMC area over time.

Table 1: Distribution of solid waste by type in the PMC area, suburban website, City Progress, city level progression section.

Month & year	Mixed	Wet	Dry	Domestic Hazardous	Sanitary
Jul-20	203	7911	5333	41	14
Aug-20	203	7911	5333	41	14
Sep-20	203	7911	5333	41	14
Oct-20	149	7938	5360	41	14
Nov-20	149	7938	5360	41	14
Dec-20	95	7979	5373	41	14
Jan-21	135	8073	5238	41	14
Feb-21	122	8046	5265	46	22
Mar-21	95	7979	5373	41	14
Jun-21	122	8046	5265	46	22
Jul-21	122	8046	5265	46	22
Aug-21	95	7979	5373	41	14
Sep-21	122	8046	5265	46	22
Oct-21	122	8046	5265	46	22
Dec-21	95	7979	5373	41	14
Jan-22	NA	8019	5382	13	40
Feb-22	NA	6302	5040	113	380
Mar-22	NA	6896	5528	118	408
Apr-22	NA	6779	5401	518	0
May-22	NA	6975	5580	421	125
Jun-22	NA	6835	5491	201	302
Jul-22	NA	6302	5040	194	299
Aug-22	NA	6835	5491	201	302
Sep-22	NA	6779	5401	118	400
Oct-22	NA	6835	5491	201	302
Nov-22	NA	6976	5581	124	402
Dec-22	NA	6935	5389	151	279
Jan-23	NA	6935	5389	151	279
Feb-23	NA	5585	3801	103	128
Mar-23	NA	5624	3908	106	132
Apr-23	NA	5779	3659	98	114
May-23	NA	5859	4053	84	94
Jun-23	NA	5468	3923	71	70
Jul-23	NA	5557	4024	86	93
Aug-23	NA	6147	4817	99	164
Sep-23	NA	7025	5908	145	289
Oct-23	NA	7260	5996	138	297
Nov-23	NA	7282	5711	130	282
Dec-23	NA	7656	5538	132	264

Jan-24	NA	7300	5231	117	235
Feb-24	NA	6848	4892	103	184
Mar-24	NA	6932	4989	101	180
Apr-24	NA	6954	4937	105	164
May-24	NA	7240	5078	136	219
Total	2025	313744	226441	4915	6670

Source: SWM Data of PMC, 2024

Waste characterization based on Amount

The data provided illustrates the quantities of various types of solid waste generated, with Mixed waste registering the highest amount at 313,744 tonnes in the specified period. Wet waste follows closely behind at 226,441 tonnes, indicating a significant volume of organic materials such as food waste and yard trimmings. Dry waste, encompassing materials like paper, plastics, and metals, accounts for 4,915 tonnes, which is notably less compared to Mixed and Wet waste categories. Domestic Hazardous waste, which includes items like batteries, paints, and chemicals that require careful disposal due to their potential environmental or health risks, totals 6,670 tonnes. Sanitary waste, which typically consists of items like diapers and medical waste, is also present at 6670 tonnes. The high quantities of Mixed and Wet waste highlight the importance of effective waste management strategies, particularly in urban areas where population density and consumption patterns contribute to substantial waste generation. Proper segregation, recycling initiatives, and waste reduction campaigns are essential to manage such volumes sustainably. Furthermore, addressing the disposal of Domestic Hazardous and Sanitary waste is critical to prevent environmental contamination and health hazards. Municipalities and communities need robust waste management policies and infrastructure to handle these diverse waste streams effectively. Overall, the data underscores the complexity and scale of modern waste management challenges, emphasizing the need for comprehensive approaches that encompass waste reduction, recycling, and responsible disposal practices to ensure environmental sustainability and public health protection.

Figure 1 presents the distribution of Mixed waste across the months from 2020 to 2021. From July 2020 to September 2020, 203 tonnes of mixed waste has been collected. From October 2020 to November 2020, it drops to 149 tonnes and remains stable. December 2020 shows a further drop to 95 tonnes. January 2021 shows an increase to 135 tonnes, followed by a decrease in February 2021 to 122, and a further drop to 95 tonnes in March 2021. June 2021 to December 2021 shows fluctuating values between 95 and 122 tonnes. The data shows a stable period at 203 for the first three months. This stability is followed by a sharp decline to 149 tonnes in October 2020, maintaining this lower value in November 2020. This suggests a significant event or change around October 2020 that caused a reduction in the values. December 2020 sees a further decrease to 95 tonnes, indicating another impactful event or change. January 2021 sees a slight recovery to 135 tonnes, suggesting a potential short-term improvement or adjustment. The values then fluctuate between 95 and 122 tonnes for the rest of the year, indicating an unstable period with no clear trend of recovery or decline.

Source: SWM Data of PMC, 2024

Figure 2 shows monthly data from July 2020 to May 2024 for Wet waste. Initially, from July 2020 to September 2020, the collected wet waste is around 7911 tonnes. There is a slight increase to 7938 tonnes in October and November 2020, and then to 7979 tonnes in December 2020. The value peaks at 8073 tonnes in January 2021 and then fluctuates around 8046 to 7979 tonnes until December 2021. In January 2022, the value is 8019 tonnes before a significant drop to 6302 tonnes in February 2022. Throughout 2022, the values vary between 6302 and 6976 tonnes. In early 2023, the values decline further to 5585 tonnes in February and 5624 tonnes in March. There is a gradual increase from April 2023, reaching 7260 tonnes by October 2023 and peaking at 7656 tonnes in December 2023. In 2024, 7300 tonnes is collected in January, showing fluctuations between 6848 and 7240 tonnes through May 2024. This data suggests periods of stability, significant drops, and subsequent recovery phases.

Source: SWM Data of PMC, 2024

For the Dry waste category, **Figure 3** shows monthly statistics from July 2020 to May 2024. In September 2020, the values stay at 5333 tonnes from July 2020. There is a minor uptick to 5360 tonnes in October and November of 2020, and then another climb to 5373 tonnes in December of the same year. By January 2021, it decreases to 5238 tonnes, and from then on, it varies between 5265 and 5373 tonnes until December 2021. There is a minor increase to 5382 tonnes in January 2022, but a substantial decrease to 5040 tonnes in February 2022. Then, during 2022, the values vary, ranging from 5040 to 5581 tonnes. Early in 2023, there is a precipitous drop, reaching a low of 3659 tonnes in April and a high of 3801 tonnes in February and 3908 tonnes in March. In May 2023, a recovery starts, and by October 2023, values had increased to 5996 tonnes. But by December 2023, it has dropped to 5538 tonnes, and by February 2024, it has dropped even lower to 4892 tonnes. By May 2024, the values had somewhat recovered to 5078 tonnes. This data shows times of stability, notable drops, and stages of slow recovery.

Source: SWM Data of PMC, 2024

For the Domestic Hazardous category, **Figure 4** shows monthly statistics in tonnes for the period of July 2020 to May 2024. The values stay constant at 41 tonnes from July 2020 to January 2021, with a small spike to 46 tonnes in February and June 2021. Until December 2021, the values will vary between 41 and 46 tonnes. There is a large surge to 113 tonnes in February 2022 and 518 tonnes in April 2022, after a steep decline to 13 tonnes in January 2022. There is a lot of volatility throughout this time, with values spiking and then falling to more stable levels. The values level down between 118 and 201 tonnes by the end of 2022. The figures vary greatly in 2023, beginning at 103 tonnes in February. The figures in 2023 are highly variable, rising to 145 tonnes in September after falling to 71 tonnes in June from 103 tonnes in February. The values fluctuate between 101 and 136 tonnes through the end of 2023 and the beginning of 2024. Over the specified period, the data shows periods of stability, notable spikes, and notable swings in home hazardous waste.

Source: SWM Data of PMC, 2024

Figure 5 shows monthly data for the Sanitary category from July 2020 to May 2024, expressed in tonnes. From July 2020 to January 2021, the values stay constant at 14 tonnes, with a small spike to 22 tonnes in February and June 2021. 40 tonnes is a significant peak in January 2022. This is followed by significant increases to 380 tonnes in February 2022 and 408 tonnes in March 2022. It's interesting to note that the value fluctuates greatly over the year, reaching a peak of 402 tonnes in November 2022 after falling to 0 tonnes in April 2022. The values are expected to remain volatile throughout 2023, peaking at 297 tonnes in October and falling to 70 tonnes in June. In 2024, the amount of production decreases gradually from 235 tonnes in January to 164 tonnes in April and then rises to 219 tonnes in May. This data shows that the amount of sanitary waste generated has substantial fluctuation and periods of stability interspersed with notable spikes.

Source: SWM Data of PMC, 2024

Discussion

Dry waste data reveals periods of stability interspersed with significant drops and gradual recoveries. Dry waste, which includes recyclable materials like paper, plastics, and metals, shows consistent levels across the months. Previous research has recommended that dry garbage be sold in metropolitan areas after being segregated and stored. The interest in selling them should rise as soon as the economic worth of this kind of garbage is confirmed, and this will raise the families' income. In urban Centres, where households already seek out services

like supermarkets and hospitals, waste may be collected on these occasions. Separating the recyclables at the source and selling them to recyclers or the city itself were other suggestions (Han Z, Liu D 2015; Lima and Paula Loureiro Paulo 2018).

The present study highlights the potential for expanding recycling programs and improving collection systems to ensure that these materials are effectively diverted from landfills and processed into new products. Research has indicated recycling has many advantages above simply reducing the amount of waste that ends up in landfills. In addition, recycling offers a valuable supply of raw materials; there are markets for paper, metal, cardboard, glass, plastic, and other commodities. Although gathering and selling these items probably won't result in a profit for the community, under certain circumstances it can lower waste management expenses by generating income from garbage (Salha Mohammed Kassim 2012). According to past studies, disadvantaged and marginalized socioeconomic groups engage in informal garbage recycling by scavenging and waste picking as a means of generating revenue, and in certain cases, even for daily survival. This is pervasive in developing-nation cities, with estimates indicating that as much as 2% of people live off of picking trash in Asian and Latin American cities. This is a disadvantaged population's adaptive response to scarcity (Berthier 2003; Medina 2000; Medina and Dows 2000).

The relatively lower but stable quantities of domestic hazardous and sanitary waste underline the necessity for specialized handling and disposal methods (Moore 2015; McDonald, S.; Oates, C.J.; Alevizou 2016). These waste streams pose environmental and health risks, making it crucial to implement robust collection, treatment, and disposal systems to mitigate potential hazards. The efficacy of sustainability policies can be increased by explicitly taking regional variations in waste management preferences into consideration when designing them (Oke and Kruijzen 2016). Within this framework, the central government's responsibility for waste management should be to assist regional governments, as they have a deeper knowledge of local waste management methods (Abbott A, S, and L 2011).

The observed variations in waste generation could be influenced by seasonal changes, economic activities, and public awareness campaigns. Understanding these patterns can help municipal authorities adjust their waste management strategies to accommodate fluctuations and improve efficiency during peak periods. The stable generation of mixed waste from July to September 2020, followed by a sharp decline in October and further reduction in December, suggests significant changes in waste generation patterns. This could be due to new policies, seasonal variations, or changes in waste management practices around October 2020. The fluctuations observed in 2021 indicate instability, possibly influenced by external factors such as economic activities or public awareness campaigns. Additional proof that effective teaching and promotion initiatives lead to good separate garbage collection has been offered by numerous research conducted in the past. According to the study's findings, the intervention group conducted the best manual separate collection of MSW and was more aware of the value of effective waste management than the control group. The two information campaigns were run differently, which is why these results occurred (the control group said that the information was almost nonexistent) (G, PS, and Read AD 2006; K and K 2009; C 2001; M and WL 2010).

The government has improved living standards over the past ten years by introducing the Clean India Mission, Smart Cities, Amruth Cities, and Digital India. The fundamental infrastructure components of these tasks include e-government and citizen services, urban mobility, affordable housing, health, education, water and energy management, and waste disposal (MoUD 2015). For instance, the city of Baroda has seen significant strides in solid waste management through the proactive efforts of its Resident Welfare Associations (RWA). These associations have organized door-to-door campaigns to generate public interest and have appointed volunteers and sweepers to manage the program effectively. A nominal fee of Rs 3-5 per household from slum areas and Rs 30 per household from other residential areas is collected to fund the transportation of waste from generation points to primary collection points, with commercial establishments contributing more. This system has ensured a well-organized collection and transportation of waste to community bins. Similarly, Kochi's waste management in 1994 was marked by the innovative involvement of a private agency, Popular Environment Management Services (PEMS), which was contracted for five years to collect waste from community bins and transport it to disposal sites. The Kochi Corporation supported this initiative by installing 350 metal bins as community waste collection points and providing 6-7 waste collection vehicles to PEMS on rent. PEMS was responsible for the operation and maintenance of these vehicles, ensuring their efficiency. Both case studies exemplify how structured collaboration between local bodies and private agencies or resident groups can enhance urban waste management systems (Kumar and R.K. 2013).

The data highlights the ongoing challenge of effective waste segregation and recycling. With mixed and wet waste constituting the majority of the waste stream, there is a need for comprehensive initiatives to promote source segregation, enhance recycling infrastructure, and encourage community participation in waste management programs (Lima and Paula Loureiro Paulo 2018). Effective waste management requires the active involvement of the community. Public awareness campaigns and educational programs can play a crucial role in changing waste disposal behaviors, promoting recycling, and encouraging the adoption of sustainable practices. The high quantities of mixed and wet waste necessitate the development of robust waste management policies and infrastructure (Demirbas 2011). Investment in waste processing facilities, such as composting plants and recycling centers, along with the enforcement of regulations, can significantly improve waste management outcomes (Singh 2020).

The data for domestic hazardous waste shows notable spikes, particularly in early 2022, followed by periods of stability and further fluctuations. These spikes could be attributed to specific disposal campaigns or increased public awareness about hazardous waste. The lack of a systematic assessment of the quantity and polluting potential of hazardous wastes is the main issue with hazardous waste management in India. The National Productivity Council, the Pollution Control Board, and the Ministry of Environment and Forests have gathered data that indicates the hazardous waste management practices now in use are not environmentally sustainable (I, SP, and DK 1996; Misra and Pandey 2005).

The volatility indicates the need for continuous monitoring and specialized handling procedures to manage hazardous waste safely. Sanitary waste data shows periods of stability, interspersed with substantial spikes, such as in early 2022. The high variability suggests that factors like changes in population health, public health campaigns, or availability of sanitary products could influence waste generation. Effective management strategies are essential to handle these fluctuations and ensure safe disposal of sanitary waste. Technically speaking, fully sustainable systems can be created, but it's unlikely that there will be a real need for them. The consumer would not be willing to pay (in the widest sense) for full screening to be implemented in the case of sanitary wastes. This can be taken into consideration by a multidisciplinary and multi-criteria decision-based approach, which may also be able to provide a "more sustainable" option that the present generation would be prepared to support in order to save resources for future generations (Ashley et al. 1999; Ashley, Souter, and Johnstone 1997).

The remarkable growth in total income from 2021 onwards indicates a significant increase in revenue from waste management activities. This growth could be attributed to improved waste collection, recycling initiatives, or increased efficiency in waste management operations. The data highlights the financial benefits of effective waste management practices and the potential for further investment in this sector. The observed trends and fluctuations in different waste categories emphasize the need for adaptive and responsive waste management strategies (Pardo Martínez and Piña 2017). Municipal authorities should focus on enhancing waste segregation, promoting recycling, and ensuring proper disposal of hazardous and sanitary waste. Continuous monitoring and analysis of waste generation data are crucial for making informed decisions and improving waste management practices. The fluctuations in waste generation data highlight the role of public awareness and participation in waste management. Campaigns aimed at educating the community about proper waste segregation and disposal practices can lead to more stable and manageable waste generation patterns (DH 2004; S, C, and KU 1994).

The analysis of waste distribution in Panvel City from July 2020 to May 2024 reveals several key trends and variations across different waste categories. Stone and mortar waste quantities are generally low, with occasional peaks suggesting specific construction activities. Wood waste remains minimal, indicating limited wood consumption or effective reuse. Waste from paver blocks and bricks shows significant fluctuations, peaking in mid to late 2023, reflecting construction trends. Metal waste remains stable, except for a peak in December 2022, possibly due to increased industrial activity. Cardboard and rubber waste show substantial monthly variations, with notable peaks indicating periods of high consumption. Non-recyclable waste exhibits a decreasing trend, highlighting improvements in waste segregation and recycling efforts. Paper and plastic waste increase over time, peaking in late 2023, likely due to heightened consumption and packaging use. Packaging material waste fluctuates, with a significant peak in December 2022, followed by a decline, possibly due to changes in packaging practices. Compost quantities show wide variations, with a peak in August 2022, reflecting seasonal waste generation. Concrete, glass, and cloth waste display fluctuations, with notable peaks indicating construction and consumption trends. Steel and inert processed waste remain low, suggesting limited generation. RDF waste shows sporadic entries, with occasional peaks, indicating selective waste-to-energy initiatives. Processed C&D waste data is sparse,

with significant entries highlighting construction activity periods. These trends underscore the need for targeted waste management strategies to address the specific characteristics and variations of different waste types in Panvel City (Suttibak, S., Nitivattananon 2008).

Conclusion

The analysis of waste generation patterns in Panvel City from July 2020 to May 2024 underscores the importance of adaptive and responsive waste management strategies to address the evolving needs of urban waste disposal. The consistent production of mixed waste highlights the need for enhanced waste segregation practices at the source, supported by robust public education campaigns and the development of appropriate infrastructure. Effective organic waste management strategies, such as composting and biogas generation, are crucial to reduce the landfill burden and create valuable by-products. These efforts align with the broader goal of promoting sustainable waste management practices that are socially, economically, and environmentally acceptable (Hassan, Jameel, and Sekeroglu 2016).

The data also reveals the significant role played by the informal sector in waste management, particularly in the collection and recycling of materials like metal, cardboard, rubber, glass, and packaging materials. This highlights the need for formal recognition and support for informal waste pickers to enhance their contributions to the recycling ecosystem. Additionally, the economic benefits derived from the sale of waste materials, such as metal, cardboard, and plastic, underscore the potential for generating revenue through effective waste management practices. Municipal services and industries' utilization of materials like paver blocks and concrete further exemplifies the effective conversion of waste into valuable resources (Vergara and Tchobanoglous 2012).

Overall, the trends and fluctuations in different waste categories emphasize the need for continuous monitoring and analysis of waste generation data to inform policy and strategy development. Public awareness campaigns and educational programs are essential to promote proper waste segregation and disposal practices, fostering a culture of sustainability within the community. The integration of advanced waste processing facilities, coupled with stringent enforcement of regulations, can significantly improve waste management outcomes. By focusing on these key areas, Panvel City can enhance its waste management system, contributing to a cleaner, more sustainable urban environment.

Investment in infrastructure, such as composting plants and recycling centers, is essential to support the management of organic and recyclable waste streams effectively. This infrastructure not only reduces environmental impacts but also generates valuable by-products like compost and recycled materials. The active involvement of the community through awareness campaigns and educational programs is critical to fostering sustainable waste disposal behaviors. Encouraging residents to participate in recycling programs and promoting the reuse of materials can further enhance waste management outcomes.

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